

Challenges faced by school administrators in school management

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Abstract. This study aimed to examine the challenges school administrators in Kepez district of Antalya faced in their communication with teachers and the solutions they found to these challenges. The research was carried out in the Kepez district of Antalya and involved seven school principals. It is a qualitative study using phenomenological design and maximum variation sampling technique. The findings of the research indicated that school principals primarily focused on their legal responsibilities, strived to fulfill their managerial duties using available resources, and placed importance on the structure based on tasks and responsibilities. While struggling with limited resources and bureaucratic obstacles, principals developed various strategies to establish effective communication with teachers and maintained their motivation. However, the research also revealed that the process of making the school climate contributing to learning and teaching was not given sufficient importance or was overshadowed by other structural and material issues. This situation might negatively affect student achievement and teacher satisfaction. In conclusion, school administrators should continuously develop both their managerial skills and communication strategies to adapt to these significant transformations in education.

Keywords: School principal, teacher, communication problems, school climate

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Introduction

The school administrator, as the leader of the school team, should be a good role model for others through their personal and professional qualities. Demonstrating good practices in educational management requires balancing internal and external dynamics of the school and adopting multiple perspectives. The contextual nature of management practices, their multifaceted character, and the combination of uncertainties, individualism, and collective characteristics make it essential for educational administrators to adopt a strategic perspective (Balci, 2011).

It is of great importance for educational administrators to continuously develop their leadership skills and remain open to innovations for the success of schools. The core competencies that school principals should possess are shaped around leadership skills. The analysis of problems, the decision-making process, and the implementation of appropriate solution strategies are fundamentally linked to the leadership abilities of school principals, and more importantly, to their instructional leadership behaviors. These skills are necessary for the school administrator to function effectively as a leader. Understanding the organizational structure helps school principals better comprehend the problems they encounter and produce effective solutions (Kaya, 1979).

Considering situation-specific differences in the decision-making process and taking these differences into account during the adaptation process are also of critical importance. These characteristics are expressed as the essential skills that school principals must possess as instructional leaders. Accurately

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analyzing problems and serving as an example during the solution process are important parts of their leadership roles (Şişman, 2011).

The management principles of planning, organizing, budgeting, and personnel selection, expressed by Western thinkers in the early 20th century, were reinterpreted in the second half of the century under the influence of human relations approaches and postmodern paradigms. Since the beginning of the 21st century, more flexible, human- and group-centered approaches have taken their place in the organizational world. Discussions in the context of democracy and human rights, along with international standards, place humans at the center of organizational life (Gümüşeli, 2001).

All these transformations in the world of organization and management inevitably affect schools, requiring school principals to be proactive in responding to the expectations and needs of teachers, students, parents, and the broader social environment. In this era, parents have become more concerned with their children's educational needs, contribute to schools according to their budgets, and hold teachers and administrators accountable, becoming a significant part of the educational and managerial activities in schools. Students, on the other hand, are more focused on their own abilities, are careful in selecting schools, strive to be an active part of primary teaching, challenge rules and traditions more often, and question the traditional roles of teachers and administrators. Similarly, teachers are also taking on new roles to meet the changing expectations of the students and parents they serve and to sustain their individual development. These changing roles, expectations, needs, and situational conditions constantly redefine the roles of school administrators, teachers, and students (Bayrak & Terzi, 2004; Çelikten, 2004).

The transformation of school principals' leadership roles has become an inevitable necessity. For administrators caught in chaos and conflict, traditional management principles are inadequate to meet today's expectations and needs. Leaders who fail to recognize the need for change and view maintaining the status quo as ideal management cannot withstand internal and external pressures (Bursalıoğlu, 2012; Şişman, 2011).

The concept of contingency management suggests that the principles emerging at the intersection of an organization's goals, members, and the expectations of its audience become the most ideal management principles for that organization. The new public management approach—emphasizing accountability, student-centered leadership, standardized criteria, information society, globalization, and multiculturalism—has significantly altered the context of educational management (Balci, 2011).

Adapting to new circumstances requires flexible rules and structures, making the perspective and value system of school administrators crucial. This has also led to debates around standardized teacher competencies (Özoğlu, 2010). Major societal problems, ideological conflicts, value crises, and economic challenges impact the relationship between administrators and teachers, reflecting broader cause-and-effect dynamics (Ertürk, 1984).

In today's complex organizational and societal dynamics, the shift from traditional, technically focused management to human-centered and flexible leadership approaches has become unavoidable (Bursalıoğlu, 2012; Şişman, 2011).

Aristotle emphasized the impact of education on both societal and individual development. Education contributes to the moral and social growth of individuals, and school administrators play a crucial role in this process (Turan, 2011).

School principals are responsible not only for administrative tasks but also for socio-psychological roles. They must empathize with all stakeholders, understand their needs, and adapt to societal and cultural changes. Effective principles develop strategies to maximize the potential of teachers and students, thereby enhancing school success (Bayrak & Terzi, 2004).

As individuals, principals should communicate with empathy, considering the family and cultural backgrounds of others. As leaders, they must share the school's values and goals with teachers and students, fostering a positive learning environment. As citizens, they should embrace societal diversity and contribute to social integration, developing healthy relationships with the community. Effective principals balance improving educational performance with a broad sense of social responsibility (Çelikten, 2004).

Organizations under environmental pressures need leaders with strong leadership qualities who can adapt and acquire new competencies. Effective communication between school administrators and teachers is crucial for successful school management and improvement of the educational environment. A management style that fosters meaningful communication and collaboration is more effective than an authoritarian approach. Principals play a central role in problem-solving and should have the necessary knowledge, experience, and analytical skills (Hoy & Miskel, 2010).

The 21st century has brought significant global changes that have deeply impacted education systems. Technological advancements, shifts in social dynamics, and economic transformations are reshaping the management processes of educational institutions. Consequently, educational institutions must adopt new management approaches, and school administrators are required to redefine their roles. School principals face responsibilities such as effective communication with teachers, improving the school climate, and enhancing the quality of education. Thus, this study aims to analyze the challenges faced by school administrators in the Kepez district of Antalya in their communication with teachers and the solutions they have implemented to address these issues.

Methodology

This research was carried using a descriptive phenomenological design, a qualitative research method based on interpretive paradigm (Gunbayi & Sorm, 2018). The phenomenological design focuses on topics that are known but require in-depth and detailed investigation (Polkinghorne, 1989). This approach aims to analyze the structures and relationships used by individuals in their daily lives to understand their social worlds and to uncover hidden meanings within verbal and written texts. Thus, This research employs a qualitative study design using the phenomenological approach, which focuses on understanding phenomena through the lived experiences of individuals. Maximum variation sampling was used to select a group of seven school principals in the Kepez district of Antalya. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, and a thematic analysis was carried out to identify themes related to communication challenges between school administrators and teachers. The study focuses on exploring the current state of communication, the underlying causes of communication problems, and the strategies implemented by administrators to resolve these issues.

This study was conducted using a descriptive method to thoroughly examine the issues between school principals and teachers. The qualitative data obtained from in-depth interviews with school principals were analyzed and interpreted based on the interview questions and themes identified during the analysis. Based on the information gathered, comprehensive descriptions of the current state of the teacher-principal communication process and potential sources of problems were attempted.

Sampling

Seven school principals who participated in the study were selected using the maximum variation sampling technique based on purposive sampling method. Maximum variation sampling aims to identify common or shared phenomena across different situations and to reveal different dimensions of the problem according to this diversity (Palys, 2008).

The data collected through interviews reflect the participants' worlds of meaning, their ways of interpreting their experiences, and their emotions and thoughts. In this method, context-specific meanings are revealed through an interpretive approach. Since meanings are culturally and socially

constructed, the data obtained during qualitative interviews are deep, rich, and detailed (Willis, 2007; Kuş, 2009).

The research was conducted in a total of 7 schools in the Kepez district of Antalya province, including 3 primary schools, 2 middle schools, 1 science high school, and 1 Religious high school. The study specifically included schools with a high number of students and teachers, including 3 primary schools, 2 middle schools, and 2 high schools, and 7 school principals were included in the research. Information about the participants is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Participant Information

Participants	Gender	Age	Seniority	Administrative Seniority	Subject	Education Level
P1	Male	41	15	7	Primary	Master's Degree
P2	Female	42	17	8	Primary	Bachelor's Degree
P3	Male	39	12	6	Primary	Bachelor's Degree
P4	Male	56	31	15	Social Studies	Master's Degree
P5	Female	37	14	9	Physical Education	Bachelor's Degree
P6	Male	49	23	13	Religious Culture and Ethics	Bachelor's Degree
P7	Male	38	16	8	English	Bachelor's Degree

Data collection

In the study, an interview technique was used, and to enhance validity and reliability, a semi-structured interview form was prepared. The method and stages of the research were explained clearly and in detail to the participants, and additional information was provided on any unclear topics. After the questions for school principals were reviewed by experts, a pilot interview was conducted with one principal. Following necessary adjustments, the main interviews were carried out. The prepared questions were open-ended, with some questions including alternative questions and probes. The interviews were conducted in a friendly conversational setting at times and places deemed suitable by the participants, with information about the topic provided beforehand. The interviews with the principals were recorded, and notes were taken during the sessions. The findings were presented descriptively, ensuring they were meaningful and consistent within themselves. Additionally, the findings were considered realistic by the individuals who participated in the research.

Ethics statement

This study adheres to the highest ethical standards in research. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and their rights before participation. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their voluntary involvement. To maintain confidentiality, participants' names have been anonymized and pseudonyms have been used throughout the study.

Interviews were conducted in a manner that avoided leading questions and were recorded with the participants' consent. The recordings were played back to participants at the end of each interview to verify accuracy.

The data collected were documented and analyzed with care, and all findings were reported accurately. Direct quotes were used where necessary to ensure authenticity, and clear, accessible language was employed to present the findings. The study complies with ethical guidelines and has been conducted with respect for the dignity and rights of all participants.

Rigour

This study has adhered to the highest standards of rigour throughout its research process. All methodological procedures were conducted with meticulous attention to detail, ensuring accuracy and reliability in every aspect of the study (Gunbayi, 2024; Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

The research design was carefully planned and implemented, with a thorough review of the literature and careful selection of appropriate methods and tools. Data collection and analysis were performed systematically and consistently, following established protocols to maintain validity and reliability. To ensure the credibility of the findings, multiple data sources were triangulated, and the research process was continuously monitored for adherence to ethical and methodological standards. Detailed records were kept of all procedures, decisions, and modifications to provide transparency and facilitate replication. The results were analyzed with precision, and interpretations were based on rigorous examination of the data. Peer review and feedback were sought to validate the findings and enhance the study's overall quality. By upholding these standards, the study aims to contribute valuable and reliable insights to the field, demonstrating a commitment to rigorous research practices.

Data analysis

The data obtained from the interviews were transcribed and used to create a framework for descriptive and content analysis. Data consistent with the conceptual framework were defined and interpreted as findings. The care was taken to use clear and understandable language in the description and presentation of the findings, and direct quotes were provided where necessary.

Findings

Communication with Teachers and Encountered Problems

The findings revealed that school principals primarily focused on their legal responsibilities, utilizing available resources to fulfill their management duties. The study highlights that principals often prioritize structural and administrative duties over the development of a positive school climate. Communication problems between principals and teachers often stem from organizational misunderstandings, ineffective communication channels, and a lack of accountability among teachers. Additionally, teachers' insufficient knowledge of organizational structures and reluctance to adopt new teaching methods contribute to the communication breakdown. The study also emphasizes that bureaucratic obstacles and limited resources hinder the effective implementation of communication strategies. Principals described the communication problems they face with teachers in management as follows:

- **Lack of Knowledge about Organizational Structure:** Teachers are often unaware of the organizational structure.
- **Ineffective Communication Channels:** Communication channels are not functioning properly.
- **Lack of Sense of Duty:** Issues such as not arriving on time for duty or not being present at duty locations.
- **Non-compliance with Class Times:** Not adhering to class start times.
- **Delayed Submission of Documents:** Delays in submitting lesson plans, activity reports, departmental documents, and other paperwork.
- **Lack of Responsibility and Sincerity:** Insufficient responsibility, sincerity, and lack of communication with parents.
- **Communication Breakdown:** Communication gaps between teachers and school administration.
- **Personal and Professional Problems:** Problems related to personal and professional life, lack of empathy, and school culture.
- **Professional Inadequacy:** Teachers' professional incompetence, burnout, errors in teacher appointments, resistance to change, and lack of enthusiasm for duties and compliance with regulations.

Principals also noted that teachers often did not know the regulations well, think individually, did not read books, and failed to renew themselves. It was noted that teachers did not know the organizational structure well and did not behave according to the hierarchy. Some teachers treated the teaching profession as secondary and prioritized their personal matters, indicating a lack of professional awareness. Inadequate knowledge of regulations and cultural differences created communication difficulties. Additionally, some teachers were reported to be unable to keep up with development and renew themselves, leading to professional inadequacy. Some statements of principals' are as follows:

"Problems related to fulfilling duties are particularly prominent, such as supervision, class entry and exit times, document submission, and responsibility towards students. First and foremost, teachers should bring their issues to us, rather than us identifying them ourselves." (P1)

"Teachers do not fully understand the regulations, and knowing them too well can slow one down. A teacher with 19 years of experience who does not know how to prepare departmental and annual plans should not be a teacher. Teachers should not be inadequately trained. There are serious issues in teacher training. Additionally, teachers do not read, renew themselves, or know the methods and techniques, especially older teachers." (P3)

"One must not forget that they are human, which is very important. Many of our teachers act in a disorganized, free, and careless manner and are quite comfortable with it. Freedom is important, but work should be done in accordance with the system. It is more accurate to say that some teachers resist change. However, there are also colleagues who do their jobs seriously and with enthusiasm. We do not tolerate those who do not fulfill their duties." (P6)

"Primary teachers should not have deficiencies in regulations and professional knowledge. The teaching profession should be proficient both in knowledge and artistic aspects. They should be open to broader criticism in their relationships. In schools where decisions are made collaboratively, there are no implementation issues." (P7)

Analysis of Communication Problems and Solutions

Traditional educational management research often limits theoretical understanding of human experiences in problem-solving, strategic planning, and implementation by excluding emotions. In this context, it is understood that school principals evaluate the problems in communication with teachers, particularly in terms of not adhering to regulations. Issues such as adherence to the hierarchy and meticulousness in regulations related to supervision, discipline, dress code, planning, and class entry times are seen by principals as major communication problems. Teachers' roles and responsibilities within the school were evaluated based on these criteria. The emphasis on technical issues such as supervision, class entry and exit, document management, daily and yearly planning, discipline adherence, professional competence, and regulation knowledge indicated that principals focused more on technical aspects rather than emotions and values in their management and communication with teachers.

Educational administrators are expected to consider both individual and school goals as well as their social responsibilities. Schools are organizations established to fulfill moral purposes and prepare youth to meet societal responsibilities. In addition to legal and professional responsibilities, educational administrators have a moral responsibility to meet societal expectations. Reconstructing the school is both a technical and moral responsibility.

Principals were observed to provide informal guidance to teachers, remind them of regulations, emphasize the importance of issues, engage in dialogue and persuasion, take preventive measures, and conduct meetings to address communication problems. For instance, P3 and P7 stated:

"First, I make sure that teacher colleagues realize the situation. I empathize, but teachers should also do the same, although they rarely see the need. Everyone thinks in terms of their own interests." (P3)

"Informal discussions are conducted with colleagues who do not fulfill their duties to provide necessary guidance. If there are professional deficiencies, it is the school administration's duty to address them. If there is intent, informal resources shift towards formal ones to avoid organizational injustice." (P7)

Principals' Emphasis on Ideal Teacher Profile

Principals prioritized teachers who were knowledgeable about regulations, self-develop, perform their duties voluntarily and with affection for students, and were respectful, tolerant, humanistic, and constructive. They preferred teachers who developed themselves both personally and professionally and valued the importance of principles. According to P1, P4, and P5:

"A teacher should be respectful, tolerant, humanistic, unifying, and inclusive. They should communicate well and have a clear mind. They should be problem-solvers, not problem-makers. They must strive to solve issues and use appropriate methods. They should diagnose and treat issues correctly." (P1)

"Teaching should be based on voluntarism. Love for humanity should be paramount. Teachers should not have excuses. They should be constructivist, perform good guidance, and engage with each student individually." (P4)

"Human values, love for the country and people, and love for the profession should be prioritized. Additionally, they should renew themselves and be enthusiastic." (P5)

The development of the education and school system is possible through effective collaboration between administrators and teachers, and the establishment of mutual trust. Principals' sincere, honest, open, problem-solving approach, proactivity, and communication with the environment are crucial for collaboration and trust. This also requires upper management to be sensitive to poor attitudes towards teachers. While regulatory knowledge is a prerequisite, qualities such as alignment with accepted societal values are prioritized by principals. Many tasks and responsibilities related to teachers were emphasized, and the ideal teacher profile was expressed by principals.

In social sciences, there is a shift from dogmatic positivism, which reduces ethical and moral issues to individual preferences and biases, to understandings that recognize organizational and public life as arenas for moral struggle and human actions. This shift, called post-positivism, post-structuralism, post-liberalism, or the re-conceptualization of traditional virtues, character, and justice, indicates a clear move away from extreme rationalism.

Problem-solving is a path to effective learning and individual skill development. It involves time, effort, energy, and practice. It is multifaceted as it involves needs, goals, values, beliefs, skills, habits, and attitudes, and combines elements such as creative thought, intelligence, emotion, will, and action. The problem-solving process begins with courage, willingness, and self-confidence. School administrators often report issues such as teachers' inability to keep up with changes, lack of communication with school management and parents, professional inadequacies, feelings of burnout, lack of empathy, and prioritizing personal matters over teaching. It is stated that problems are inherent wherever there are people.

Issues Related to School Management

In the context of issues related to school management, the difficulties faced by school principals in managing schools, solutions to challenges within the school, and opinions on effectively and successfully managing the school have been examined. It appears that, beyond communication with teachers, environmental and material resources that affect the school preoccupy school principals more. In other words, when it comes to management, principals focus more on the level at which they can manage the school with the resources they have, expressing that they are compelled to prioritize material resources over human resources.

The difficulties encountered by school principals in school management concentrate on issues such as lack of parental involvement, communication deficiencies, absence of support staff, cleaning, heating, deficiencies in teachers and equipment, inadequate planning related to teaching, insufficient activity of parent-teacher associations, and inadequate school budgets. Additionally, simple bureaucratic obstacles that cannot be overcome are also mentioned as other factors exacerbating the situation. The lack of attention to cleanliness in an environment with hundreds of people and the absence of necessary funds for this are considered significant health-related issues. It is emphasized that schools are left alone in terms of financial resources, forced to manage with a tight budget, and the requirement for free and compulsory primary education is an additional factor putting administrators in a difficult position. In this context, P6 and P4's views are as follows:

“Cleaning is a very important issue; there are 210 people in my school, but there is not a single permanent cleaning staff. The school needs to be cleaned every break. If you employ someone, it is a financial burden. You want to provide technical support in the classroom, but there are financial shortages. School principals have no planning related to education and teaching. We are constantly doing menial tasks and holding meetings, which I can't say are very effective... The changes being made not being conducted by people with an educational background creates problems both theoretically and practically.” (P6)

“Electricity, water, and heating costs are covered by the special administration. On the other hand, the absence of support staff is a problem in itself... Firstly, our schools have been left to their financial fate. The amounts we collect under donations often do not solve our problems. My school has 25 teachers and 600 students; its budget is 30,000 TL, of which 15,000 TL is used for the four support staff and their insurance. The remaining amount is used for various needs of the school. How do you think 600 people can be managed economically?” (P4)

It is understood that school principals sometimes feel helpless due to financial constraints when facing problems in management and try to solve these within the hierarchical structure, often without achieving the desired results. It is also noted that principals' participation in numerous meetings negatively affects school management. Moreover, problems based on financial issues, such as cleaning, lack of support staff, and activating parent-teacher associations, are seen as the most emphasized problems by principals.

In recent years, with the impact of changes and developments in social, economic, political, and technological fields, educational initiatives and school management are increasingly moving away from centralization. Especially, the interest of parents, civil society organizations, and local institutions in education and schools, and their desire to participate in educational decisions are growing each day. In many countries, the responsibility of those benefiting from these services in providing educational funding is changing the nature and boundaries of school-community relations. With all these changes and developments, it is expressed that managing today's schools with a classical approach is no longer feasible.

School principals expressed that they tried methods such as addressing the root cause of the problem, consulting, delegating tasks, working in collaboration, benefiting from experiences, managing according to individuals, and reminding of organizational hierarchy. In this regard, P3, P2, and P6 state:

“First, I try to address the issue by understanding and analyzing it well. Then, I consult with my management team and school family association members to prioritize the importance of the issue and take necessary actions. I also involve school boards in the matter and make sure to document everything in the decision book, meaning I have a collaborative management approach.” (P3)

“A school principal must be very good at crisis management. Experience is very important; problems encountered do not surprise us in later years. 450 people require 450 different management styles.” (P2)

“Each school is structurally different. Since the goals and resources of the school vary, the problems will also differ.” (P6)

It is emphasized that since schools are structurally different, problems will also differ. School principals underlined the importance of understanding the root cause of the problem, activating boards and associations, being proficient in crisis management, and adopting a management approach based on individual needs. Principals also stated that to manage a school successfully, it was crucial to establish a good structure, form a good management team, make decisions collectively, act sincerely, and uphold institutional culture by sharing problems. In this context, P3 and P6 state:

“The understanding that ‘the principal manages the school’ is incorrect. If you say ‘I know everything,’ it is impossible to work harmoniously with that staff or participate in a social event. If you do not value people’s opinions, they will not value you and will not embrace the institution or the organization. You must definitely be a leader, not just a principal.” (P3)

“The institutional culture must be good. The institution should take ownership of its staff and also the problems. It should be sincere and convincing in solving problems. Additionally, it should have a philosophy of covering faults, generating solutions, planning, and addressing the root causes of problems. We should conduct self-criticism and be engaged in teamwork. We should also recognize our shortcomings and seek support.” (P6)

As a cultural leader, a school administrator should spend time and energy enhancing traditions, group norms, and shared values in the school environment and should be able to take preemptive measures to address potential problems. It was mentioned by school principals that they tried to solve financial problems with their own means and that they did not have sufficient resources to address financial issues. As a result, it was emphasized that it was not the principal alone but the management team, formed boards, and other assigned management members who managed the school, highlighting the importance of teamwork.

Conclusion and Discussion

This study examined the challenges faced by school principals and their reflections on school management. The findings revealed that school principals experienced issues related to the school budget, support staff services, education, and the environment. Principals primarily expressed concerns about managing the school budget and general and administrative services. While it is important for today's administrators to address problems with tailored approaches depending on the person and situation, presenting different solutions to the same problem can hinder consistency in institutional culture. Due to the principals' incorrect attitudes and behaviors, there may be a lack of trust among staff, leading to decreased organizational commitment, job performance, and job satisfaction, ultimately causing issues to arise spontaneously. Thus, it is crucial for school principals to maintain consistency in organizational management.

School administrators developed both formal and informal solutions to problems encountered within the organizational structure. When teachers, students, parents, and other environmental factors that constitute the organization are guided in accordance with the school culture and climate, problems are resolved before they start. However, when a positive relationship is not established among these dynamics, conflicts cannot be prevented. School administrators typically start by identifying the problem and aim to resolve it through consultation, while also utilizing informal methods. At times, they resort to formal solutions. The problems encountered, which vary by individual and institution, lead to different solution proposals, as emphasized by some administrators. The role of principals in leadership is considered crucial in the communication process (Tahaoglu & Gedikoğlu, 2009).

Principals faced various obstacles in fulfilling their leadership roles, which often result in not meeting the desired level of performance. Decision-making and problem-solving are fundamental to the

management of any organization, including schools. Schools, like other social institutions, are affected by social, economic, cultural, political, scientific, and technological developments, both positively and negatively. Adapting schools to these changes and developments is among the tasks of school management. In this context, school principals need to possess the necessary knowledge and skills for decision-making and problem-solving (Çinkır, 2010).

Principals generally adhered to regulations in their practices, considered the professional competencies of teachers, support teamwork, and create a constructive competitive environment within the school. They also ensured that teachers contributed to decision-making processes.

As stewards of both societal and ethical responsibilities, school administrators must embrace a profound sense of accountability towards all levels of society, both horizontally across different sectors and vertically through various tiers of governance. Their role encompasses a significant responsibility towards students, who are entrusted to schools during a critical developmental stage when they are particularly vulnerable. Ensuring the safety, growth, and education of these students—who are often in a state of fragility and susceptibility—represents a fundamental aspect of their duty. Their goal is to nurture these young individuals into well-informed, constructive members of society.

From a professional standpoint, educational administrators are expected to foster environments that support the ongoing professional development of teachers. Ethically, they must cultivate a workplace characterized by trust and sincerity, ensuring that teachers feel valued and respected. Legally, it is crucial for administrators to uphold and protect teachers' rights and entitlements (Starratt, 2004). Administrators are tasked with aligning their role with the broader social order, adapting its principles to fit the specific context of the school (Fullan, 2004). The school environment should facilitate professional collaboration and trust between teachers and administrators (Barnett & Fallon, 2007).

The findings from this study indicated that participating school principals tended to prioritize legal responsibilities over other dimensions of their role, such as professional and ethical obligations. They managed with the resources available to them and place significant emphasis on maintaining the organizational structure crucial for effective human resource management both within the school and in interactions beyond it. However, the results also suggested that instructional leadership—critical for teacher development and support—was often overlooked or inadequately addressed by principals. This neglect can lead to an environment where the focus on creating a supportive learning and teaching atmosphere is diminished by pressing structural and material challenges (Aslanargun, 2016).

Furthermore, the study highlighted a need for greater attention to the psychological and social factors that underlied communication issues within schools. Effective management requires not only addressing these elements but also recognizing the importance of social capital in fostering a conducive school environment. Future researches should investigate these areas to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how school leaders can better navigate and resolve the complex issues they face, ultimately enhancing the overall educational experience for students and staff alike.

Recommendations

In consistent with the results obtained, following suggestions can be put forward:

Financial resources for schools and financial transparency to address budgetary constraints should be improved

Adequate resources and personnel for school maintenance to ensure a healthy learning environment should be allocated

Professional development programs for school leaders on leadership, crisis management, and effective communication should be put into action.

Effective communication and collaboration mechanisms among teachers, parents, and other stakeholders should be strengthened

Leadership approaches that enhance school culture and staff engagement should be supported.

Psychological counseling and social support services within schools should be enhanced.

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Conflicts of Interest

No conflict of interest has been declared by the authors.

Author Contributions

Ramazan Burak Kahyaoğlu: Conceptualization, data curation, investigation, methodology, writing original draft, review & editing

Kenan Yavuz: Data Collection, review & editing

Bülent Uludağ: Data Collection, review & editing

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Declaration of Competing Interest

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Ethics approval

In the writing process of the study titled “**Challenges faced by school administrators in school management**”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the authors of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data. “Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER] and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be encountered, and all responsibility belongs to the authors and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Institutional review board (IRB) approval

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 17 decision numbered 375 on September 10th, 2024.

Data Availability Statement

Anonymised data from this study can be made available on request from burakcan0071985@gmail.com